

What Is Vidnami?

[Vidnami](#) is an online video creator software that allows you to produce fast, easy, and professional-looking videos within short minutes.

You can use it to create a quick video for social media sites, blog posts, influencer videos, instant ads, sales videos, online courses, property listing.

Vidnami Features

[Vidnami](#) is the continuous upgrades and improvements to the system.

Some of the recent updates have impressed me; for example, one of the upgrades they made late last year was the addition of automated voice overs.

Vidnami has fourteen different texts to speech voice-overs that will read the script for you.

Not only that, but unlike many of the other software tools with text to speech technology that sound robotic, Vidnami voice overs are the most realistic I have heard.

However, you can also add your voice or any music track. Vidnami provides a wide selection of royalty-free tracks, or you can upload your own.

Another exclusive update they made was partnering up with Storyblocks videos, which give you access to 350,000 [HD video clips](#) that you can use for any videos you create with Vidnami.

Storyblocks has its monthly subscription plan, but with access to the Vidnami, you will have access to all the HD clips you need without the extra costs.

Other features include;

- **Over 125 million stock images**
- **Adding watermarks**
- **Full motion video backgrounds**
- **Over 40 video templates**

Vidnami creates professional looking videos that attract more viewers. These videos can get you viral video views. You can easily create the "Top 10" type videos to build an authority YouTube channel.

And the unique thing when you use [Vidnami](#), it will not require you to install any application on your computer or laptop. Vidnami is hosted on Amazon's web server. So you don't need to install anything.

It takes all of the features of other video makers. It combines them into one excellent online tool that every internet marketer or small business owner, you don't need to download or install anything on your computer.

And best of all, Vidnami offers a 7-day trial without the need for a credit card, so you know they won't just automatically take your money after your trial ends as many companies do.

Vidnami 7-Day Free Trial

Plus, right now, there is even a 7-day free trial offer going on.

It means that you can try the tool risk-free (and get to keep any videos you create with it) without spending a single dime.

Then, if you see Vidnami is for you, you can opt to get it.

If not, you'll be able to cancel your account again, without spending any money, no questions asked.

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